

The
University
of Nowhere

A note on the text:

This story is an outcome of the University of Nowhere project, which consisted of a series of three seminars on utopia and higher education and collaborative creative writing.

The title and concept of the story come from William Morris's utopian novel of 1890, News from Nowhere, which describes a future English utopia. "Nowhere" does not seem to have a university, only a vague reference to "colleges on the mainland," which we took as an invitation to imagine one.

As the reading list for the seminars shows, this initial idea was put into dialogue with contemporary analysis of political economy (Benanav), other, post-scarcity utopian writing (Le Guin), pre-war critical theory (Horkheimer), and readings from pedagogical (Pereira) and sociological (Connell) studies. More context for the task of imagining a future university was provided by the ever-greater incursions of machine learning ("AI") into the working processes and daily lives of scholars, and ongoing precarity of academic labour. The speculation of an energy crisis in the story is no doubt influenced by the closure of the Strait of Hormuz during the period of its composition and editing.

Below is a list of the participants of the seminar series and writing activities, who between them participated in discussion, prepared reading and seminar tasks, contributed to the chapter's contents, and edited the contributions into the eventual form of the story.

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Seminar 1: Utopia as “choosing between possible futures”

William Morris, *News from Nowhere* chapters I to V.

Aaron Benanav, “Beyond Capitalism 1: Groundwork for a Multi-Criterial Economy” (sections 1-8), *NLR* 153.

Seminar 2: Academic Life after Capitalism

Aaron Benanav, “Beyond Capitalism 1: Groundwork for a Multi-Criterial Economy” (sections 9-end), *NLR* 153.

Max Horkheimer, “Traditional and Critical Theory,” trans. Matthew J. O’Connell, Continuum.

Ursula Le Guin, *The Dispossessed* (chapter 3), Harper Collins.

Seminar 3: A Post-Academic World? Knowledge Production and Sharing in Nowhere

William Morris, *News from Nowhere* Chapter XVIII “The Beginning of the New Life”

Irène Pereira, “Éducation,” in Jérôme Baschet & Laurent Jeanpierre (eds.), *Mondes postcapitalistes* (2026).

Raewyn Connell, *The Good University: What universities actually do and why it's time for radical change* (chapters 7 & 8)

A small group of travellers climbed onboard the bus and made the usual calculations as they came up the aisle: take the first place available or hope for something better further back. It was only evening but many of the passengers had already attempted to settle into sleep, leaving various detritus on any spare seats next to them to discourage the new arrivals from picking them as neighbours. Laura decided to take a seat nearer the front in order to keep her distance from the toilet cubicle, which she knew from experience would leak faint, foul odours during the journey. She made a polite enquiry and the woman spread across the seats moved her bag onto the overhead shelf and shimmied over to the window seat without returning a word.

It had been a nuisance to make it out to this edge-of-town bus station and Laura gave herself a chance to shed some of the tensions of getting here and of the prospect of an uncomfortable night ahead. But a recent conversation with family came to mind, uncalled for. *You know we hoped you would pick a more secure profession.* Her seat was hard and she experimented with the footrest options. A different voice: *I don't mean you should take a job anywhere, but at this stage in your career it's important to be flexible.*

They started moving and as the front wheels caught a pothole, the bus lurched and the strap from her neighbour's bag swung down and knocked the top of her head. She tucked it back away without getting up. *We appreciate your interest in the application. And for giving us the opportunity to learn more about your profile and goals.* The disappointment of this recent rejection still made her wince when she remembered it: *We have decided to move forward with another candidate whose experience more closely aligns with the requirements of this role.* She had made it to the final interview round, a fact that merited at least the politeness of an email from the search committee chair. The strap swung down again and struck her ear. Laura stood up this time and jammed the whole bag further back. They were now on the motorway and the lights went down. She eased the seat back an inch and tucked a scarf under her ear. There was now a steady engine noise and the tyres hummed on the smooth road surface. The language of the letter inviting her to this interview had been different from others. *We look forward to your visit, come with an open mind.* Laura felt herself easing already into sleep, hoping—once again—that this time things might turn out differently. She needed to sleep and started going through sums to take her over the threshold. How much had this trip cost her? The bus ticket was 60 euros—so if one meal averages 5 euros, that's 12 meals. One night in a hotel room was 75 euros, 15 meals. There was the option of a hostel for 35 euros, or 7 meals. She had decided to spend 8 meals to have a room of her own for the night after the interview: justified as a treat for having to go straight from teaching to the bus to the interview. Even so, fluffy euros were jumping over fences and disappearing towards the horizon...

It seemed only that I had closed my eyes but when the bus jolted to a halt and the driver announced “end of the line!” I saw that it was bright, morning daylight. I stumbled down the stairs, only half-awake, set my bag on the pavement and looked up. There was a shelter and behind it a tall green hedge. A gust of wind brought a pleasant whiff of fresh air and I allowed myself to take a deep breath. When I turned to the driver to ask if this was indeed the correct stop, the bus had already left without my noticing. My phone showed 09:30, so I had little less than half an hour before my interview; my nerves immediately started up at the thought of speaking about my research interests, answering the inevitable question of what challenge I had successfully overcome at work. Where was the entrance to this place? The first thing I needed was a place and some time to freshen up. My phone was showing no signal. I felt very out of time and place.

There was a rustling behind me and a woman some years older than me came up to me and said *hello* in a friendly way. She was no doubt a Professor, with the professional security to wear such a loose, colourful dress. My own outfit was rather crumpled and tight. “You must be here for an interview!” she exclaimed. I was taken aback. “Yes, are you here to meet me?” “I can show you around, call me Mowi!” “Laura Ospite,” I hurried to say. “Yes of course! Nice to meet you. Laura Ospite.”

She took my elbow and we walked toward the wall of tall green; I saw that there was a first and a second hedge, and between them a gap of around a metre, along which we walked. The thickness of the branches on both sides and above us muted the noise of any sounds other than a few birds chattering as we followed this tunnel a little while, before it opened on our left into a wide open space. “Welcome: The University of Nowhere!” she exclaimed, raising her arms in a triumphant manner.

The sun was gaining in strength, and during the walk up the gentle slope to the university buildings my shirt started to feel sticky. We had reached a landscaped lawn plain, with inclines rising on both sides and steps and ramps here and there that led up to the buildings. The ground felt soft under my steps. It was covered in a sort of lush vegetation with a reddish hue to its small furry leaves. A few people were sitting in small groups on the ground or lounging sleepily where the lawn seemed to form little cushy spots. We came down a central pathway that was lined with tall trees, whose trunks were wide at the base and looked every bit as old as the colonnaded buildings. Mowi spotted me admiring them and said: “Some Fellows planted them here some five years ago.” “Five years?” I repeated, thinking I had misheard. She shrugged, “They are fast-growing—that is the whole point, I think. I don’t always stay up to date with the experimental plantations going on. A new improved species, most likely.”

We walked silently for a few metres, admiring the thick branches that provided a pleasant shade to the path. “So,” I began again, “I assume you have a bio-engineering start-up here?” My guide paused to think a few moments. “Oh, you may be coming from one of the few places that still have

technological innovation centres,” she finally said. “I have always found poetic the way you talk about ‘new technologies’ as if they were actual things and not ongoing bodies of knowledge. I can’t wait to know more, but don’t worry, I will spare you the repetition and will wait for everyone to be there!” She seemed to be choosing her words very carefully and added: “The University of Nowhere does not have laboratories in the sense of places where scientists build technical devices in the name of progress. I hope I’m clear enough; these things seem so natural to me that I’m not used to describing them!” It was only bafflement at the thought of such a different organization of knowledge that made me pause in silence. I would have to make some late changes to my presentation on knowledge systems in higher education.

“But the trees?”, I asked instead. She laughed: “All inventions you will see here are product of a temporary, often spontaneous gathering of fellows around a specific desire of creation. To be honest I haven’t made my mind yet about this sort of crafted genetic manipulation. What is certain though, is that these trees were very welcome in such a devastated area, though their effect on local ecosystems has been carefully monitored—in fact a number of discoveries on the interaction of tree species and fungi have been made as a result. State and commercial funding systems had some advantages to them, but room for creativity and accident was not one of them.”

I had been forming a list of objections as Mowi talked and this last point provoked me to speak. “State *and* commercial funding systems? They are so different I don’t see how you group them together. One provides uninterrupted autonomy, the other wants results.” She gave me a sharp look at this point: it seemed that Mowi was thinking how she could explain something in terms a child would understand. “We generally take the view that the distinction was always precarious. And their co-existence always left the door open for autonomous research to be whittled down to allow more resources for the other.” We had stopped walking and stood in the shade of one of these large evergreens. “Take these trees: we thought of the long-term benefits of a tree variety that was suited to the new climate, resistant to the toxicity in the soil, and could allow us to think and enjoy the outdoor spaces again. The idea was popular and we sent a team to Japan to research varieties of Japanese Yew trees that were thriving on the slopes of Mount Fuji after the war. The trip became even more expensive when they decided to bring several large trees back by sea-freight. But here we are.” Her laugh rang bright along the little avenue.

“Quite astonishing!” I agreed, while thinking to myself that this university seemed to place excessive value on eccentric experiments. I saw some of the younger people stretched out on the grass in conversation and wondered how this institution, with its gardens and attractions, dealt with the problem of idlers. “How long, if I may, do people generally stay here in this wonderful place? How long does it take to get a degree? Or, if I may, how long did it take for you to become a Professor?”

“Degree” she said, as if tasting an unfamiliar fruit. “I suppose I know what you mean. In the past, the knowledge produced had to be quantified and shipped off in the form of “graduates” to the labour market—or indeed the next level of education. But we have since done away with that, there really has been no need to rank people according to their supposed knowledgeability. From what I have been told, the previous system started to break down when the number of jobs requiring degrees collapsed and there was a general reckoning as to what *degrees* were for. So we turned back to certainties: that the desire for knowledge has no end limits; or indeed automatic starting age. What does it matter if the mystery you have taken an interest in takes two years to unravel or twenty? I myself came to study communication science only in my prime of life. I have acquired a good understanding now, and some specialist expertise (if I can boast for a moment), but have only recently started to *profess* this learning to others. That was the other part of your question, I believe?”

The answer was, I must say, quite irritating. Mowi seemed to have no consideration at all for my own situation—being here and on my best behaviour in the hope of being offered a job. It was the same complacency that came with job security the world over. I also found that the whimsical nature of her, or the institution’s, research policy grated against my sensibilities, habituated as they were by the priorities of impact, outcomes, and the ever-elusive *excellence*. It seemed—no, I started to believe—that I had visited another era. Of course, I bit my lip and quizzed her some more with an insincere smile.

“But how do you measure progress, how do you know *when learning has taken place*? When the students have understood and can use the content of their courses? I suppose what I’m asking is a question about evaluation.” My guide smiled gently and my annoyance subsided a little. “I see you are wedded to the ideas of good old Lord Chancellor Bacon, who would interrogate nature as if it was nursing a deep secret that could only be extracted by brute force. This was education like hunter-gathering of the old times! We do not see knowledge as an animal to be stalked and compelled to provide for us, but rather as a free growing field whose ends are always beyond the curve of a hill. We see a university as a space where travellers from different routes stop by to compare notes, to discuss, and to correct one another’s maps, little by little. It has been long recognized that the old universities, ever since the scholastic origins of those institutions, have been training people to replicate, to a certain degree of conformity, what their masters taught them. Our historians have traced the evolution of research degrees: would you imagine that, in the seventeenth century, degrees would be granted after a defense, by a student, of theses already written by a Professor? In those times one could resort to independent bureaus, or information agencies, to talk and satisfy one’s curiosity and questions. Later, in the nineteenth century, degrees became a measure to determine professional standing and give one credentials to be a member of the society in a certain role, which also involved measuring the student’s capacity to replicate knowledge and performing certain actions. This philosophy of learning was refined into ever-more formal systems, eventually governed by the infamous imperatives of *learning outcomes* and *constructive alignment*.

“After the digital collapse, when so many records of degrees and qualifications were lost, it became apparent that the world would have to continue somehow or other. The younger generation started to challenge those above them in age and seniority, asking them to *prove* their credentials. It hastened the recognition that we could no longer rely on a system that had existed for so long that it seemed inevitable... until it was gone.” The phrase ‘digital collapse’ was not strange to me: we sometimes brought it in as a hypothetical in conversation, from which to discuss scarcity, possible consequences, and transformation of our institutions and ourselves. With Mowi’s mention of this as an event that had taken place in the past, I could no longer ignore that I had somehow ended up in the future, or a dream of the future, built from ideas and elements that were already in the air. ‘The future is already here,’ we had regularly quipped, *pace* William Gibson, ‘it is just unevenly distributed.’ Here I was, in fact or fiction, and the realisation did not change my need for secure employment—so strong an attachment that it had survived the journey across time.

Mowi interrupted my thoughts. “But let me now ask *you* a question, given these words you use that now seem strange and antiquated to me. Is it the influence of your mother tongue? Here we are speaking in English but if you would prefer, we might speak in Italian or German; I don’t suppose you know Greek, which happens to be my mother tongue. It is always a pleasure to find compatriots or admirers of our language and culture, though I suppose that those who know me in one language have a very different sense of me from those with whom I speak a different one. Tell me, which languages do you speak well enough of to work in at a university?”

I replied in Italian, though I did not know it well, and had not spoken it for some time. The muscles of my face and mouth resisted the vowel sounds. I asked what were the languages of *insegnamento* but regretted the question straight away: presumably this was the sort of information that I would normally—somehow!—have prepared before this interview. How does one prepare for the future?

“Seminars take place in whatever language happens to be known by the group members. When someone has reason to believe that there will be enough people to start a regular series of conversations on a subject, they put an announcement up on the notice boards, in the language of the seminar. Sometimes they also put this in English, so that others might see it and tell a friend. We do use English as a common language in this sense, but since the realignments that took place in the early twenty-first century, we have found ourselves moving ever further away from relying on it as a *lingua franca*.”

“That is very progressive,” I replied, not sure how the word would be understood, “but doesn’t that limit the classes to very small numbers?” She thought about this for a moment before answering. “What you say is true, but we rely on discussions to continue outside the seminar, and we also believe that actual, human *translation* is the most constructive form of repetition, for it stops ideas from being too much solidified in particular language forms. If an idea does not travel any further than its seminar room, it probably needs more work! And if a seminar only has a handful of people in attendance, it

can be shut down at any time. The work of teaching means that those doing it want their seminars to be taken by as many as can constructively contribute; for other exchanges there are the many opportunities here for conversation—those are what led to seminars being offered in the first place. There was a time, it's true, when such a way of doing things seemed unthinkable, shocking even, but we have fortunately overcome those times, partly, many of us theorize, due to the energy crisis of the mid twenty-first century.”

She seemed to have warmed to this subject, so I thought I would take a risk and make the most of her earlier comment. “Let’s imagine I *am* someone from the past, explain this theory to me: tell me how this change came, from the dominance of English to this paradise of many languages.” She looked at me with gentleness, as if she knew my secret and was happy to proceed with this game of dissembling so that I might learn something; either that or the gentleness was pity and she had already decided that there was no position for me here in Nowhere.

We were shaken out of these thoughts by the sounds of heated discussion that were coming from the room we were now approaching. Rather than hurrying past, Mowi put her arm on my shoulder to indicate that this was something we should stop and look at. Through the glass doors, we could see that a woman was on her feet and gesticulating passionately as she spoke to the room. Behind her was a projected image that seemed to be something like a Gantt chart with various bars in different colours; she turned to a small computer and one bar lengthened as another become shorter. “Is this a presentation of research findings?” I asked.

“Not at all,” she answered, “though it does affect what research is given approval, and which tools are to be used. That is a bi-annual resource allocation meeting, which always involves argument—because the decisions about where to spend our computation resources determines the fate or success of projects. In the end, someone will be deeply disappointed, at which point they might withdraw for a period into the tunnels, but we have not found a better system than voting across the entire institution once a shortlist has been drawn up—that shortlist is what is being decided in there.”

“Who usually gets their way? Is that person speaking now making the case for the impact of the research for society and its special claim on public funds?” This at least seemed a familiar way of going about things. “Is that how decisions are made where you are from?” she replied. “I don't imagine there is such a thing as a perfect model, but pretending to know the impact of something in advance must be problematic, as any attempt to anticipate the future must surely be. For that reason, we always reserve some compute allocation for projects that are selected randomly. It allows for projects to go ahead whose value may not have been obvious to us. It cannot correct our blind spots, but at least it allows for projects to persist despite them.”

She checked the meeting schedule, which was posted outside the door for any who cared to read and after a moment turned back to me. “They are now at the part of the meeting where they evaluate the project’s efforts to minimize energy use and also the harm that might be expected as a consequence of offloading intellectual labour onto machine systems. If you like, we could listen in.

We entered the hall where a scientist was arguing fiercely, “What has greater impact? Asking a hundred scholars to waste their time on reading materials that don’t interest them, or asking a machine to do it in hours? I’m sorry but I cannot agree with your assessment.”

“Dolores, I understand you are upset, but if you cannot motivate people to join the project, then perhaps you should reevaluate the interest that this project actually engenders.” The problem seemed familiar, even if the way of setting out the problem was a little different from what I was accustomed to. “Does the funding not cover research assistants?” I whispered to my guide, who replied, also *sotto voce*: “Ah of course, I have heard of this role before, in more stratified systems. No, here we cannot coerce young scholars with the carrot of career advancement and the stick of unemployment. If they cannot convince someone to do the work, then they have to decide for themselves if it is worth doing on their own.

“The worst years are behind us thankfully—I mean that long period of the energy transition that, when it came, so few were prepared for. Our models for approving research developed in the period when markets were forced to reprice fossil fuel futures drastically higher and there was a desperate contest for electricity. We actually have a history project underway that is trying to represent the many changes that so overwhelmed my parents’ generation at the time when the new machine systems had drawn so much capital and value with the promise of reduced wage expense. And of course whole energy systems had to be moved over to electrified generation. The period of war and actual fighting is so happily forgotten though we live in its aftermaths. Out of this crisis, we and our partner institutions had to bring different criteria into our systems of planning and investment, I mean for instance the long-term radiation poisoning of energy use while fusion stations were still part of our energy mix, the labour implications if a project needed heavy amounts of computation power—whether for calculation or translation—and even the influence of energy use here on the expenditure of heating credits elsewhere. We entered an age of scarcity, which made the nature of our research more... *Spartan* you could say. But I have taken too long to tell you things you know already; you probably mean the same thing when you talk about ‘impact’! I should really live more by the principles of austerity that I am talking about. Your concision is admirable.”

My guide announced that we were approaching the canteen (or *mensa*, as Mowi called it). The whole morning had been so strange that I had not thought of food at all. The corridor had small windows that looked back out at the gardens on the left, and a much larger window that opened our view to the inside of the building. On the other side of the glass, a group of people was busy chopping vegetables and peeling potatoes, all wearing the same neat brown aprons. I slowed down. The scene reminded me of those restaurants where you could see chefs at work, except the large working kitchen here was

clearly designed to feed large numbers rather than a select clientele. At the same time, the kitchen seemed to be a kind of gathering space, and a number of conversations were taking place around the large island-stations where food was being prepared or cooked.

Mowi noticed my interest. “They are from the conference on ‘History of Food in the Eighteenth Century.’ I have high hopes for the fruits of their labour. Last week we had the ‘Intellectual Thought in the Early Modern Low Countries’ event and I’m still recovering.”

“A conference with cooking?”

“Well, yes. Actually, we try as much as possible to combine the necessary tasks of everyday life with the intellectual ones. It would be sad only to study and talk; just as it would be sad to be restricted only to the maker areas and not the learning rooms! Of course, some enjoy cooking so much that they come here every day, or volunteer in the kitchens for certain hours of the day as an antidote to stiffness from too much sitting and thinking. They have effectively become the custodians of the kitchens and everyone listens to their advice as well as enjoying their work. And then some come here to study but move on to being in charge of eating and conversation spaces elsewhere.

I stared again through the glass. A flustered young man was running about with a smoking pan, followed by chastisements from someone with wooden spoon who seemed to have some position of seniority. The young man wiped pearls of sweat off his forehead with a sleeve and did not seem to be enjoying the situation. “He’ll learn,” Mowi laughed.

“But is there even any time left for the actual conference?” This perplexed my guide, judging by her arched eyebrows. “What do you mean ‘actual conference’? People coming together, working together, talking together, isn’t this what a conference is? Look at the two over there, in the corner.” I could see the ones she meant. Their hands were working fast. One of them was washing carrots, piling them up in front of her colleague, who handled his sharp knife with ease. Their mouths moved even faster. I couldn’t hear what they were saying but it was clear they were deeply involved in both of their tasks.

“What other jobs do you ask conference delegates to do? Cutting hedges?” I asked, recalling the immaculate gardens. The question came out sounding more sarcastic than I had intended. Mowi did not seem bothered, fortunately. “Oh yes! It depends on the season, and on what people are able to do. There’s sometimes one or two hours of quiet study in the morning. The rest is up to everyone’s imagination. Ah, wait. You can see for yourself here.” A piece of paper was taped to the kitchen window. The title at the top read “Eating the eighteenth century: afternoon programme.”

12-14:30 Cooking (from 12) and lunch (from 13:30). Meet in the kitchens. Do not be late!

14:30-16:30 Collective reading of our new members’ current work. Please ask Demi for a copy of the chapters.

16:30-17:30 Break with refreshments. Optional: Walk around the gardens.

Somebody had added in handwriting: “18:30 A pigeon has been stuck inside the amphitheatre since this morning. If you can climb up a ladder, come help us!” My guide sighed. “They sometimes overdo it and ask conference-goers a little too much in the way of chores. This pigeon is a recurring issue that we really ought to deal with.”

I thought I might use this notice as a pretext to find out more about this unusual university. “In this case, would ‘Demi’ be the organizer of the conference, or a junior person? It’s all very casual. Is that always the case, or just how the head of the scientific committee does things? And if you don’t mind my asking, in an institution without qualifications, how do you choose the head of a scientific or even a search committee?” I gave my best attempt at a disarming smile, in case Mowi thought this enquiry inappropriate. By now I should have known she would notice the strangeness of my question, though of course it was this entire university that was strange to *me*.

“You really do speak just like the book I have been reading in these last few days about twentieth-century academic life!” Mowi exclaimed. “But that must be your way of drawing out knowledge—please continue, it will help me give the best account I am able of our university. As to your question: Why should those positions not be occupied by any fit person? Does it not become quickly clear to you, when listening to someone speak, if they have expertise that they can share with you for your benefit? Of course, you can never rule out that someone will embellish their work with empty phrases for the pleasure of hearing themselves talk. But those cases are rare now, I believe. Only those who are passionate about sharing their knowledge go to the trouble of holding conferences or initiating courses, and they take great pride in being extensively prepared. Or a group of people will come together to explore together what they are interested in, in which case no one wants to hear a person taking longer than they need to and robbing others of their precious time.” I nodded along, still flustered by what felt like a rebuke, and tried to appear as if it all sounded quite natural.

“Which is,” Mowi was saying, “if you think about it, a vast improvement over the universities of old, where even those who were not the least bit interested in holding lectures were obliged to do so, just so that they could continue to call themselves by the title of Professor and secure a position of authority that they then held onto for dear life. And to save them from the embarrassment of speaking in front of empty theatres, attendance at those events was made mandatory. Really, it was often a waste of everyone’s time.”

We stood in silence for a moment. “Come on now, they still need a bit of time till lunch. We have time to pay a visit to the library before”. I followed her, but cast a glance into the mensa, where the other conference delegates were filing in to take their seats.

As my guide and I continued down another avenue lined with hedges, a man’s chest and head appeared suddenly in front of us on our path, then climbed up and into full view.

“Goodness,” I exclaimed, before managing to produce an apology for the man. He said nothing and hurried past, barely looking at us. “Where did he come from?” My attention fell on a small break in the hedge, where a shadowy flight of steps led underground. “He must be taking a retreat,” Mowi replied. “A retreat from what?”

“Some of the scholars prefer isolation and solitude, either for a time or for the entirety of their stay here. During the war, tunnels were built as bomb shelters and to protect precious materials. They later discovered that natural galleries already existed underneath them, so it was light work simply to connect them. There is an extraordinary variety underground: a luminescent variety of mushroom has been discovered down there and the passageways glimmer with silicate minerals. Some scholars have now found a use for this network: holing up in one of the caverns for silent work, holding seminars that they wish to keep private rather than open, or simply exploring the tunnels’ natural structures! The network is so vast that it’s impossible to run into anyone down there. And if you follow the tunnel network, you might have no idea where you might pop up out of the ground. I’ve not taken much time to explore them myself, but there are different entrances around the institute. One tunnel, apparently, comes out in a cupboard by the mensa, which is very handy for those living underground. Other tunnels lead into town.”

I glanced once more at the small break in the hedge, half-expecting another scholar to rise from the earth; part of me wanted to descend into this tunnel immediately. I was worried Mowi would take it as a sign that I was not enjoying her tour, though, so I followed her along the path. Soon, something else caught my attention. A group of students were huddled together in garishly coloured gowns of crimson, violet, and lime green. They broke apart in a flourish, fumbled through a few steps, and reformed into another huddle, whereupon they began the same movements again. I was about to ask Mowi what they were doing when something on the facade to my left caught my eye: small, round marks scattered across the wall at eye level. At first, I thought they were stains. Then, as I stopped, I saw them for what they were. “Yes, bullet holes”, Mowi said, as she turned back towards me. She took a moment before continuing.

“You know, the University had a troubled history in the lead-up to the war. This building used to house one of the institutes that was meant to undertake cutting-edge research in the field of machine learning. Except, both government and funders eventually attempted to remove restrictions on the use of this any other automations, and in the climate of the time, that decision had terrifying consequences. Some researchers resisted by destroying years of their work, others stopped working in protest. The retaliation was violent.”

Mowi was lost in thought for a moment, then cleared her throat. “You may learn more when I show you our library” she said, pulling me back into the present. “We put a lot of effort into reconstructing these days and preserving people’s memories. There were almost no paper archives left, so we relied on testimonies. We also carried out a kind of collective archaeology here at the

University: old servers, maintenance rooms, sealed offices, fragments of lists, deleted logs, minutes from meetings that no one had meant to preserve. That is how I learned most of this.”

We had moved closer to the bullet holes. I could see the wall hadn't been repainted in that area, the holes stark against the bare concrete.

“You know, the Rector himself—that is what they called the person with most authority—called in the police in the early days of protests. Can you imagine how estranged he had become from the staff and students? Though when you think of it, it is not that surprising. Democracy had been in long decline at the University.”

“So how did you end up getting to *this*?” I gestured to the gardens and the hybrid trees but meant everything I had seen so far on my visit. “To the University of Nowhere?” Mowi smiled. “I would say it was a combination of drastic actions, which led to equally drastic changes to the institution. The involvement of the town where our university is located was essential. And we had some luck, too. At the time, students rose against the Rector and the administration, some of whom were ousted while others embraced the new situation with enthusiasm. The government responded by cutting all funding. For a time, the university became an island. Food and other basic resources were collected from benefactors that the Professors and students were able to bring onside. But the lion's share of the support came from the local communities who discovered common cause with the university: the upheavals were happening elsewhere too. The desperate conditions reminded everyone of the obligation we have to each other, to keep thinking and sharing with them, not only about them, or even for them.

“Since this new system seemed to just about sustain the life of the body and the mind, the university was able to pool resources with other universities that had also broken away from state protections. They were strange times. My father had just begun his studies, here. He talked about the barricades built by the students when the police had arrived. And students were beginning to organise their learning for the first time. They called it ‘student-centred learning,’ a bit of a joke from the old pedagogy. This time, the division between student and professor dissolved; they all became scholars. Learning became embodied, slow, often collective, the opposite of just focusing on tests of knowledge, which were called examinations; or, for researchers, on the need to publish as quickly as possible.”

I remembered how I had checked and compared my colleagues' *h*-index scores. “In the end, after the government's collapse, there was no one who could oppose the course the University had taken, and it managed to formalise its funding ties as well as its new structure of learning and researching.”

Mowi turned to point to the students wearing those strange garments, who were now arguing exaggeratedly amongst themselves. Two factions had formed and were energetically demonstrating some dance moves. “In two weeks' time, we will have a festival to commemorate this time when the community fed and clothed us. These students are practicing for the procession. They'll dance through

the streets, asking for money from the community, who might ask them to dance, to fix something in their house, or quiz them on their studies. The students will oblige, but if their dance or work is not satisfactory, they must give up their cloak of learning to the residents. Some of the local children study for months, trying to find something that will stump an expert! If they do, and no one can answer their question, the child takes the cloak (they are the relics of old ceremonies) and continues with the procession. Sometimes a scholar who cannot answer a question will just take off running and the kids give chase. It's quite a spectacle. In this way, the cloaks will pass from person to person, throughout the community, until we meet at the end of the night, for food, dancing, and wine. It's a lovely tradition, I hope you will join us to celebrate sometime."

"I would very much like that," I answered in earnest, thinking about how much had changed, and whether I would be able to stay to see this ritual of the gowns—a word that Mowi seemed to have forgotten.

Mowi pulled me through a large modern arch, and I saw that we were now in front of an entirely different building, whose walls curved away from me on both sides, making it hard to estimate its size. Before the glass doors slid apart to let us through I caught sight of myself and Mowi walking side by side towards the entrance—she with an air of distracted purpose, while I myself seemed to be diminished by this rapid sequence of new views and customs. I made myself stand a little straighter.

We entered the large circular space of the central room, off which a circuit of smaller spaces radiated at ground floor. They looked like those cubicles universities would sometimes have available for discussions and online meetings. I was learning not to ask every question that came to my mind. (What had become of Zoom and Teams?) Some rooms were occupied by lively discussion, sound-proofed into mime, other had one or two figures bent over in concentrated study. We approached the grid of desks with walking space between that occupied most of the centre of the room. There seemed to be around a hundred desks, almost all in use, and we entered a zone of white noise from breathing, chairs scraping, the tapping of keyboards, the clunk of some devices being sprung open or pressed closed. We were close enough for me to see that the steel frames were scuffed and dented in places; the chipboard of the tables was gently erupting where the surface of the worktop had cracked. The carpet was in bad shape too and had obviously been replaced where the chairs wore through it, judging by the different hue of the sections that had been less exposed to daylight.

Mowi looked at me noticing the disrepair and shrugged. "Yes, it's getting a bit shabby, but we make things last as long as we can and no has suggested that the quality of our work is terribly affected. As you can see, this is where people come to listen and think on their own." I followed her gaze and turned to look at this sea of desks and readers, before noticing how many of them were wearing headphones. Now it struck me that there were very few books visible. I could only see a few

bent paperbacks and scuffed hardbacks laid out on the desks. Nor were there the expected piles of reference works inside the smaller rooms that I could see into through the glass, nor were there stacks anywhere.

“Where are the books?” I couldn’t help asking. Now Mowi looked surprised and even a little offended. She asked in a voice louder than seemed appropriate for a library, “Surely you also suffered a great loss of books, as so many libraries did?”

I found this difficult to imagine. “In our case,” Mowi continued without waiting for my reply, “our technologists managed to get hold of a warehouse full of unused compact disks. We already had text to voice software, so we improvised a solution— “audio books”—and that has done us reasonably well. Some people call it technological scavenging, though I find the term a bit derogatory. We are slowly building up a new collection of books under the Nowhere University Press imprint but there are different opinions on how to use our collective resources. Whether to reprint what was seen to be the most important works of the past, or to print and preserve new ones. We do what we can. Oh, and the living books system is also of great benefit.”

“Living books?” I had heard of some strange things in Nowhere, but this I particularly struggled to comprehend.

“Yes, so that students and researchers may talk with books directly.”

“You seriously mean, people can talk... with books?”

“Why, being able just to read—even worse, read just summaries—that must have been the saddest thing! Let me introduce you to one of our living books.” We had reached a door, outside of which a card had been placed into a frame. It read:

Carlo

Part-time memory keeper

Part-time book: The Structure of Scientific Revolutions, Thomas Kuhn

My first reaction was to turn to my guide, who was standing right behind me, and I swear I saw a glimpse of humour in her eyes when I asked her: “You mean to tell me, living books are people?” “Absolutely. I am sure you will be keen to talk to Carlo, he knows a great deal about the history of our University. You see, with living books, you find their room and get comfortable—people usually come with questions—and you get to talk to the book and ask questions, for example about a specific passage or theme. The living books are almost always very friendly and it’s very handy to interact in this way.”

Mowi knocked on the door, from which we heard a faint “Come in.” An elderly man was sat in an armchair and was putting on a pair of glasses when we shuffled inside. Carlo’s face lit up as he recognised Mowi. “Welcome, welcome. Another university tour today? Have you been enjoying our stay with us so far?” he asked, turning towards me.

“It has been most... surprising. I think I still have to adapt to some things from Nowhere. For example, this whole living books business. You teach this book? *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions?*”

“In a way. But here, our colleagues and I prefer to say that we *are* the books we teach. I have read it so many times I could recite it in my sleep. I offer my voice to whomever wants to read it; I have recorded it many times, and many more times I have sat in a room with a listener in front of me. I have done this for decades.”

“Decades? When did you start?”

Quietly, Carlo reached into a drawer and pulled out a picture. It showed a group of five young people wearing graduation gowns and smiling. I recognised Carlo, somehow it looked like he hadn’t changed glasses all this time.

“My friends, who are there on this picture—most of them passed long ago—they did not get to see how things turned out for this university. But they started the process of becoming books, when we were graduate students. As a protest, at first. When the new guidelines came from the government, forcing higher education institutions to use Artificial Intelligence to enhance their productivity... and when it became clear the University would rather turn against us, their students, their workers, instead of protecting us...” Carlo’s voice trailed off, then he shook his head slightly. “My friends, they began spending hour after hour learning words by heart. Following words with their index on the printed page. As slowly, as deliberately as possible. You wouldn’t guess how many people you could anger just by taking your time.

“When the protests reached their highest point, and the University as we knew it collapsed... In the decades that followed, it became more important than ever to become books. Because of the war, and the collapse of many digital platforms. No books were safe. So, we read them, learned them, nurtured them, passed them on to others. Many say this kind of practice has stopped being necessary, but I wonder, how do you know when something is truly needed? I have already begun training the book who will become my successor.”

We left Carlo when a student (or scholar) interrupted our conversation, asking for Carlo’s expertise on paradigm changes. Somehow, I was crying a little bit and felt immediately embarrassed. I had never heard of an interview in which somebody cried during a campus tour and then got the job. Actually, I had never heard of anyone crying during an interview; if anything, it happened afterwards. But I didn’t have much time to pity myself. Mowi was already leading me out of the library, through wide archway.

“Now we are almost where the learning and discussion happen. I have to leave you now to run an errand: that pigeon is causing more nuisance, I am afraid. But my colleague Gwynn will take you

through the last part of the visit. I will make sure to be in time for your opening and the conversation after. That room there, with the students just leaving now. He is expecting you.

I entered the classroom a few minutes too late to hear any of the conversation on *A Theory of Knowledge*, which had just ended. At the front, the person I assumed was Gwynn was wiping the board clean. On the upper corner, a phrase remained:

Knowledge IS?.... Objectivity relevancy

The latter words had already been crossed out and others already wiped away. I stood still, my bag still on my shoulder. I was not sure if I should speak.

“You had something you wanted to ask,” he said, without turning. It was not clear how she knew. I stepped a little closer, eyes still on the board. “You wrote objectivity and relevancy, Gwynn, as if they were conditions. Or virtues.”

“Yes.”

“But they are crossed out.”

“They were under discussion. We reached the conclusion that they were not *pre*-conditions for knowledge.” I hesitated, then went on, more quickly than I would have chosen. “If objectivity and relevancy are not what qualifies knowledge—then what does? And why call the course *a theory* of knowledge at all? Why does knowledge have to be theorized?”

Now he turned.

“May I ask what you studied?”

“I am, by training, a sociologist,” I said. “Though I am... thinking of switching fields. Perhaps something like the governance of knowledge—if you follow.”

There was a slight pause.

“Governance,” he repeated. “Will you tell us what that means?” I almost smiled. “That is precisely the difficulty.”

“Perfect! ‘Difficulty’ is an excellent place to begin in my experience. We can go now into the learning room, for your presentation. Our students will certainly be interested in what you have to say and will no doubt raise problems of their own. Come with me.” He led me out of the first room and I noticed how worn with use its door was: smooth and slightly indented where countless hands had applied the necessary pressure to swing it open. A trickle of young people were entering and a group was already engaged in lively chatter. The format seemed that of a demonstration room, of anatomy or instruments designed by human ingenuity. There were half-circles of desks that rose in tiered levels, concentrating attention on the lectern and demonstration table. I realised that the room was already two-thirds full and Gwynn ushered me towards the lectern. “Feel free to put your notes here if you have them—it can be raised or lowered as you prefer. And of course you should feel free to move around as you talk. Whenever you feel like stopping, just take a seat somewhere in the theatre and the conversation will continue or someone else will come down if they choose to speak more formally. If you’re ready, I’ll introduce you.

Gwynn got up and managed to gather everyone's silence and attention. "Good afternoon everyone, thank you so much for coming to listen to our visitor, Laura Ospite. She will be opening our conversation today, whose subject is 'the difficulty of knowledge without preconditions.'"

I looked up and around the curved rows. Some faces were turned towards me; others looked aside or down, but there seemed to be a welcoming readiness to listen. Mowi had come in through a door at the back and gave an encouraging smile. I took a moment to gather my thoughts and began to talk.
